

Genetic evaluation & utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Sources of disease and insect resistance in selections of improved plant type

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Incorporation of disease and insect resistance into improved germ plasm is a major objective of the IRRI GEU program. The several donor parents that have been used as sources of resistance to each major disease and insect have poor plant type (tall with weak stems and droopy leaves). They were crossed with rices of improved plant type such as TN1, IR8, IR262-43-8, and IR24. Semidwarf lines with good grain quality and resistance to specific diseases or insects were selected and evaluated for several seasons and intercrossed to develop lines with multiple resistance. The combining ability of each line was determined from the performance of hybrid progeny that resulted from a series of crosses involving the line. Only the progeny with good combining ability were saved.

We used several sources of resistance to each pest and disease except grassy stunt virus, for which *Oryza nivara* is the only source of resistance. For blast, such donor parents as Gam Pai 15, H 105, Sigadis, Nahng Mon S-4, Dawn, Zenith, Kam Bau Ngan, and Tetep were used. For bacterial blight we used Zenith, Malagkit Sungsong, TKM6, Sigadis, Wase Aikoku 3, BJ1, and DZ 192. For tungro, we used Gam Pai 15, TKM6, Peta, Pankhari 203, Malagkit Sungsong, HR21, C013, and Ptb 18.

Five genes for resistance to green leafhopper are known; three of them have been incorporated into rices of the semidwarf plant type. Of the four known genes for resistance to brown planthopper, two have been transferred into selections of improved plant type. Genes for resistance to different diseases and insects have been studied in various combinations.

A list of 110 selections, with data on their parents, their accession numbers, and their reactions to blast, bacterial blight, tungro, and grassy stunt diseases, and to the green leafhopper and brown

planthopper, is available at the IRRI plant breeding department. The lines may be used instead of tall donor parents in hybridization programs as sources of disease and insect resistance. Scientists in national programs may obtain lists of these 110 elite lines, and their seeds, from the IRRI Plant Breeding Department.

Impact of semidwarfs on the area planted, production, and yield of rice in the Punjab of India

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The landlocked state of the Punjab lies within latitudes 29°30' to 39°30' north and longitudes 73°55' to 76°50' east in the Indo-Gangetic Plain of northern India. One of the smaller states of India, it has an area of 50,376 sq km which is alluvial in nature. It has two main crop-sowing seasons, the rabi (October – November) and kharif (June – July). The important rabi crops are wheat, gram, barley, grapes, and mustard. The main kharif crops are rice, maize, cotton, groundnuts, bajra (pearl millet), and sugarcane. The Punjab gained importance for its wheat production which increased by more than 2½ times: from 1,900,000 tons in 1965 – 66 to 5,300,000 tons in 1975 – 76. Average wheat yields have gone up from 1.2 to 2.3 t/ha over the same period.

Rice yields in the Punjab are among the highest in India. Rice now seems to be the most profitable kharif crop. The traditional rice varieties such as Jhona 20, Jhona 277, Jhona 349, Palman 246, Basmati 217, and Basmati 370 are weak strawed and tall (150 – 200 cm). They lodge badly when fertilized, so their yield is stabilized at around 1 t/ha. Rice cultivation was previously confined to fields where no other kharif crop could be grown – fields that were waterlogged or affected by salinity or alkalinity. After the introduction of varieties of the semidwarf plant type that are responsive to high fertilization – such as Taichung Native 1 in 1965, IR8 in 1968, Jaya

IRRI can provide scientists with seeds and a description of 110 elite rice lines that have been selected for disease and insect resistance. A major aim of IRRI's GEU program is to incorporate resistance into improved germ plasm. Rizal Herrera, senior research assistant, plant breeding, makes cross.